

Project Implementation Plan

Water-ForCE

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26.02.2021	V1	Version revised and approved by the Executive Board
01.03.2022	V2	Version revised and changed according the EC review report considerations in 9.2 and 9.3 sections.

List of Acronyms

AB	Advisory Board
AGA	Annotated Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
CT	Coordination Team
DoA	Description of Action
DMP	Data Management Plan
EB	Executive Board
EC	European Commission
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
FA	Funding Authority
GA	Grant Agreement
GAs	General Assembly
GPDR	General Data Protection Regulation
PIP	Project Implementation Plan
PM	Person-months
PO	Project Officer
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
TL	Task Leader
WG	Working Group
WP	Work Package

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1.- Executive Summary

The Project Implementation Plan (PIP) of the Water-ForCE CSA aims to be a reference document for the consortium members during the implementation phase of the Action. This document will summarize all the needed practical information for successfully execute the Action. The PIP will develop the operational part of the Action, based upon the information included in the Water-ForCE Grant Agreement (GA) and Consortium Agreement (CA); thus, aiming at guiding, in a practical way, all the steps and processes to be taken by the beneficiaries until the end of the Action.

The Project implementation Plan will be a living document, continuously updated if any additions or changes should be made during the lifetime of the Action. Any of these changes will be evaluated and agreed inside of the Consortium Bodies, timely consulted and informed to the EC Project Officer, and finally registered in the history of changes.

Disclaimer

The Information, documentation and figures available in this deliverable are written by the Water-ForCE Consortium members and do not necessarily reflect the view of the EC.

This document is partly based on the EC's official documents however, no legal responsibility can be taken for the contents in this document. Any doubt regarding administration and reporting should be solved by consulting the official documents or through the Coordination Team, who will consult for an official EC response, if necessary.

2.- Introduction

This PIP (formal Deliverable D8.4) aims at being a guidance for the beneficiaries of the Water-ForCE CSA during the operational implementation phase of the Action, thus leading to a delivery according to the Description of Action (DoA) included in the GA. This document is intended to be used by all the project partners, to ensure quality assurance of project processes and outputs and to timely identify possible deviations from the project work plan.

This document describes the main project data, activities and outputs; summarizes the structure, procedures and available tools for the implementation of the Action. It presents information about the rights, roles and obligations of each partner, governance procedures and communication strategy, and provides also guidance on administering, monitoring and reporting following the EC requirements stated in the Annotated Grant Agreement (AGA).

This Plan is based on several key documents/meetings including:

- The Water-ForCE Grant Agreement (NUMBER 101004186)
- The Water-ForCE Consortium Agreement signed by all beneficiaries.
- Water-ForCE Kick-off meeting (26th- 28th January 2021)

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this PIP is overruled by the Water-ForCE GA (including its Annexes) and the CA.

3.- Project Overview

3.1.- Project goal

The overarching objective of the Water-ForCE project is to develop a Roadmap for the Water Component for the future Copernicus Services, addressing the current disconnects between remote sensing and *in situ* observation research, and to deliver clarity in terms of the needs and expectations of the public and private sectors of the core Copernicus Programme and the wider research and business innovation opportunities.

Water-ForCE will bring together experts on water quality and quantity, in policy, research, engineering and service sectors. This will include operating Copernicus Services (Land, Atmosphere, Marine, Climate Change, Security, Emergency) and Networks (Copernicus Academy and Copernicus Relays), ESA, H2020 projects and international organizations as well as public and private research organizations. By working with these communities Water-ForCE will deliver:

- A Roadmap for the water component of future Copernicus services defining which is the most optimal way forward.
- Technical requirements for future Copernicus missions to fulfil better inland and coastal water related needs.
- Enlarged service portfolio, containing higher level biogeochemical products, and improved performance of the current products.
- Closer cooperation between remote sensing, *in situ* and modelling communities, in order to build an optimal network that provides necessary information about inland and coastal waters to policy makers, managers, researchers and general public.

3.2.- Work Packages and Lead Beneficiaries

Water-ForCE work concept consists of four overarching WPs and four technical WPs (see Figure 1). The **first overarching WP (WP1 Policy, stakeholder and service analysis)** will analyze current and coming policies, end-users needs, innovation needs, need for supporting water related UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), etc. The WP1 will organize one open international workshop that will synthesize the initial findings of the WP1 and provide tasks to the technical WP's (WP2-5).

The **technical WPs are:**

- **Water quality continuum (WP2)**
- **Water quantity (WP3)**
- **Aligning *in situ* and satellite Earth Observation activities (WP4)**
- **Modelling and data assimilation (WP5).**

Each of the technical WPs will gather a working group (if possible, in cooperation with ongoing international activities) which will analyse the current and future Copernicus services from their specific perspective. This will include organizing at least one thematic workshop, regular electronic meetings, and trainings (at different levels from PhD students to policy makers) within each of the technical WPs (2-5). The working groups will coordinate their activities as much as possible to support cross-topic discussions. Some of the working groups meetings will be organized back to back with international conferences and workshops or as special sessions in these events. **Each of the technical WPs will produce their recommendations for the Roadmap.**

The **second overarching WP (WP6 Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services)** will summarize the findings of each technical WP and produce the first draft of the Roadmap. WP6 will organize also an open international workshop where the first draft of the Roadmap will be discussed and analyzed. After that the WP6 will provide a consensus Roadmap, as the final outcome of the Water-ForCE project, to relevant bodies like the European Commission, ESA, EEA,

national space agencies, national monitoring offices, research community and industry.

The third overarching WP (WP7 Dissemination and communication). WP7 will start from the beginning of the project in order to bring all relevant parties to the initial workshop and promote the importance of the Roadmap for policymakers, managers, industry, and research community.

The last overarching WP (WP8 Project coordination and management) will take care of smooth progress of the project and fulfilling all the obligations stated in the contract.

Figure 1.- Schematic work plan of the Water-ForCE project.

A last WP was stated by the EC (**WP9 Ethics requirements**) that will ensure compliance with project ethics requirements.

WPs and WP Leaders

		Leader	Co-Lead	PM
WP1	Policy, stakeholder and service analysis	DotSPACE	USTIR	44
WP2	Water quality continuum	UTARTU	VITO	51
WP3	Water quantity	VUB	Antea	48
WP4	Aligning in situ and satellite Earth Observation activities	EMU	USTIR FVB-IHG	50
WP5	Modelling and data assimilation	IHE	CREAF	35
WP6	Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services	USTIR	UTARTU	26
WP7	Dissemination and Communication	IsardSAT		32
WP8	Project Coordination and Management	UTARTU	3edata	49
WP9	Ethics requirements	UTARTU	3edata	-

Table 1.- List of WPs and lead beneficiaries

3.3.- List of deliverables

Deliverables

WP	N°	Title	Lead Benef.	Nature	Diss. Level	Est. Del. Date
WP1	D1.1	List of stakeholders	USTIR	Report	Public	31/07/2021
WP1	D1.2	Sectoral policies and legislation	DotSPACE	Report	Public	31/10/2021
WP1	D1.3	Links within and between Copernicus programme	DotSPACE	Report	Public	28/02/2022
WP1	D1.4	End-user needs	ICCS	Report	Public	28/02/2022
WP1	D1.5	Business opportunities	DotSPACE	Report	Public	28/02/2022
WP1	D1.6	Satellite EO, SDGs and climate indicators	USTIR	Report	Public	28/02/2022
WP2	D2.1	Water Quality Working Group	VITO	Other	Public	31/05/2021
WP2	D2.2	Recommendations on Copernicus products - Water Quality	FVB-IGB	Report	Public	31/05/2021
WP2	D2.3	Atmospheric corrections	VITO	Report	Public	31/12/2022

WP2	D2.4	Higher-level biogeochemical products	UTARTU	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP2	D2.5	Technical needs for future Sentinels	CNR	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP3	D3.1	International working group in water quantity remote sensing	ANTEA	Other	Public	31/03/2021
WP3	D3.2	Copernicus products - hydrological	ANTEA	Report	Public	31/05/2021
WP3	D3.3	Copernicus products and services - water management	VUB	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP3	D3.4	Water resources modelling	IHE	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP3	D3.5	Sentinel missions for inland water quantity	CREAF	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP4	D4.1	Working group for in situ and satellite EO monitoring	EMU	Other	Public	30/04/2021
WP4	D4.2	In situ data-intensive monitoring	PML	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP4	D4.3	Combining in situ and earth observation data	USTIR	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP4	D4.4	Alternative monitoring methods	FVB-IGB	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP4	D4.5	New higher-level products	EMU	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP4	D4.6	Standardization and open science	NIRDBS	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP5	D5.1	Copernicus EO needs for modellers and decision makers	IHE DELFT	Report	Public	30/06/2022
WP5	D5.2	Copernicus Services and Products - Modelling	CREAF	Report	Public	31/10/2022
WP5	D5.3	AI for accurately correcting systematic forecast errors	ANTEA	Report	Public	31/10/2022
WP5	D5.4	Integration of satellite EO and modelling	IHE	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP6	D6.1	Capacity Building	USTIR	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP6	D6.2	Priorities for Research and Innovation	PML	Report	Public	30/04/2023

WP6	D6.3	Business Innovation and Service Delivery	USTIR	Report	Public	30/04/2023
WP6	D6.4	Roadmap: First draft	USTIR	Report	Public	30/06/2023
WP6	D6.5	Roadmap. Final	UTARTU	Report	Public	31/12/2023
WP7	D7.1	Public communication and dissemination plan	isardSAT	Report	Public	30/06/2021
WP7	D7.2	Website and communication tools	isardSAT	Website	Public	31/03/2021
WP7	D7.3	Workshops materials	isardSAT	Website	Public	31/12/2021
WP7	D7.4	Events dissemination and communication	isardSAT	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP8	D8.1	Management Structures	UTARTU	Report	Public	31/01/2021
WP8	D8.2	Interim Technical report	3edata	Report	Public	31/12/2022
WP8	D8.3	Templates	3edata	Report	Public	31/05/2021
WP8	D8.4	Implementation Plan	3edata	Report	Public	28/02/2021
WP8	D8.5	Reports on WP meetings	3edata	Report	Public	30/06/2023
WP8	D8.6	Reports on Major Workshops and Boards	3edata	Report	Public	31/08/2023
WP8	D8.7	Data Management Plan. First version	3edata	ORDP	Public	30/06/2021
WP8	D8.8	Data Management Plan_2	3edata	ORDP:	Public	30/06/2022
WP8	D8.9	Data Management Plan. Final	3edata	ORDP	Public	31/12/2023
WP9	D9.1	POPD - Requirement No. 2	UTARTU	Ethics	Confid	31/03/2021
WP9	D9.2	POPD - Requirement No. 3	UTARTU	Ethics	Confid	31/03/2021
WP9	D9.3	POPD - Requirement No. 4	UTARTU	Ethics	Confid	31/03/2021

Table 2.- List of deliverables and lead beneficiaries

3.4.- List of Milestones

Milestones			
Milestone N°	Title	Lead Beneficiary	Est. Del. Date
1	WP1 participants Workshop	DotSPACE	30/04/2021
2	WP1 Input to the Roadmap	DotSPACE	30/04/2022
3	WP2 participants Workshop	UTARTU	31/05/2021
4	WP2 Input to the Roadmap	UTARTU	30/04/2023
5	WP3 participants Workshop	VUB	31/03/2021
6	WP3 Input to the Roadmap	VUB	30/04/2023
7	WP4 participants Workshop	EMU	31/05/2021
8	WP4 Input to the Roadmap	EMU	30/04/2023
9	WP5 participants Workshop	IHE DELFT	31/03/2021
10	WP5 Input to the Roadmap	IHE DELFT	30/04/2023
11	Roadmap test	USTIR	31/07/2023
12	International stakeholders Workshop	isardSAT	30/06/2021
13	Final Workshop	isardSAT	30/09/2023
14	Kick-off meeting	UTARTU	31/01/2021
15	EB and AB 1st meeting	UTARTU	28/02/2021
16	EB and AB 2nd meeting	UTARTU	31/05/2022
17	Interim report	UTARTU	30/06/2022
18	EB and AB 3rd meeting	UTARTU	30/06/2023

Table 3.- List of milestones and lead beneficiaries

3.5.- Summary of Project Effort in PM

Project Effort									
	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	WP7	WP8	Total PM
UTARTU	2	12	2	3	1	7	2	6	35
dotSPACE	9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	16
isardSAT	2		2	1		1	12	1	19
Antea	1	1	7	2	3		1	1	16
PML	1	3	1	3	1	3	1	1	14
FVB-IGB	2	3	2	6	2		1	1	17
GeoEcoMar	2	2	2	2	2		1	1	12
ICCS	4		2	2	2		1	1	12
USTIR	7	4	2	6	1	10	1	1	32
IHE	2	1	2	1	7	1	1	1	16
EMU	1	2	1	7	2	1	1	4	19
NIRDBS	1	1	1	3	1		1	1	9
VUB	1	1	11		2	1	1	1	18
3edata	1	2	1	5	2	1	1	22	35
CNR-IREA	2	3	1	2	1		1	1	11
VITO	1	9	2	2			1	1	16
BOKU-IHG	2	2	1	2			1	1	9
CREAF	2	2	6		5		1	1	17
SIN	1	1	1	1	1		1	1	7
WI		1		1	1		1	1	5
Total PM/WP	44	51	48	50	35	26	32	49	

Table 4.- Project effort in PM.

3.6.- Project Planning

Figure 2.- Gantt Chart

The summary of the Project Planning can be seen in Figure 2. A more detailed Gantt Chart with identified dependencies between tasks and deliverables is presented as Annex I.

3.7.- Project Budget

Project Budget (€)						
	Direct personnel costs(actual)	Direct personnel costs(unit)	Direct costs subcontracting	Other Direct C.	Indirect Costs	Total Costs
UTARTU	210,000.00	0.00	0.00	19,000.00	57,250.00	286,250.00
DotSPACE	80,000.00	0.00	0.00	10,000.00	22,500.00	112,500.00
isardSAT	85,500.00	0.00	0.00	10,000.00	23,875.00	119,375.00
ANTEA	120,000.00	0.00	0.00	12,000.00	33,000.00	165,000.00
PML	102,200.00	0.00	0.00	16,000.00	29,550.00	147,750.00
FVB-IGB	112,200.00	0.00	0.00	9,000.00	30,300.00	151,500.00
GEOECOMAR	53,400.00	0.00	0.00	12,000.00	16,350.00	81,750.00
ICCS	70,800.00	0.00	0.00	11,000.00	20,450.00	102,250.00
U STIRLING	233,440.00	0.00	0.00	18,000.00	62,860.00	314,300.00
IHE DELFT	162,800.00	0.00	0.00	13,000.00	43,950.00	219,750.00
EMU	66,120.00	0.00	0.00	10,000.00	19,030.00	95,150.00
NIRDBS	37,800.00	0.00	0.00	8,000.00	11,450.00	57,250.00
VUB	149,994.00	0.00	0.00	8,000.00	39,498.50	197,492.50
3edata	124,940.00	32,560.00	0.00	89,000.00	61,625.00	308,125.00
CNR	49,500.00	0.00	0.00	13,000.00	15,625.00	78,125.00
VITO	197,856.00	0.00	0.00	12,000.00	52,464.00	262,320.00
BOKU	54,000.00	0.00	0.00	7,000.00	15,250.00	76,250.00
CREAF	74,100.00	0.00	0.00	8,000.00	20,525.00	102,625.00
SINERGISE	39,200.00	0.00	0.00	8,000.00	11,800.00	59,000.00
WI	41,250.00	0.00	0.00	9,000.00	12,562.50	62,812.50
TOTAL	2,065,100.00	32,560.00	0.00	302,000.00	599,915.00	2,999,575.00

Table 5.- Project Budget.

4.- Project Organization and Governance

The organization and governance of the Water-ForCE consortium is structured around two main figures: The Coordination Team and the Consortium Bodies (General Assembly (GAs), Executive Board (EB) and Advisory Board (AB)) who will work in close cooperation.

4.1.- Coordination Team

The Coordination Team is composed by the **Coordinator** and the **Project Manager**.

The Coordinator (Prof. Tiit Kutser; UTARTU) is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Funding Authority (FA). The Coordinator shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the GA and the CA.

The coordinator will coordinate legal, financial, scientific and technical part of the Water-ForCE project. He will fulfil all the tasks defined in the Article 41.2 of the GA, assisted by the Grant Department and Financial Department of the UTARTU as well as by the Project Manager. The Project Coordinator will perform the financial management of the project fulfilling all the obligations reflected in the GA and is the central contact point with the EC. The Project Coordinator will chair the project EB, GAs and support the AB.

The **Project Manager (Carmen Cillero; 3edata)** will be responsible for the administrative and documentary management of the project. The Project Manager will collect, archive and maintain all the scientific and technical documentation of the project and assure internal communication and information sharing between the members of the consortium.

The Project Manager will implement a dependence mapping of tasks; milestone and deliverables scheduling; provide templates for reporting and develop a data sharing structure with different level of access. The Project Manager will compile the WP Progress Reports received from the WP Leaders to support the Project Coordinator in evaluating the Project progress and in reporting to the EC. She will be also responsible for the development of the Data Management Plan (DMP).

In particular, the Coordination Team shall be responsible for:

- monitoring compliance by the Parties with their obligations
- keeping the address list of members and other contact persons updated and available
- collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables (including financial statements and related certifications) and specific requested documents to the FA
- Develop the 3 versions of the DMP.
- transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other Parties concerned
- administering the financial contribution of the FA and fulfilling the financial tasks described in the GA and CA.
- providing, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents that are in the sole possession of the Coordinator when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims.

If one or more of the Parties is late in submission of any project deliverable, the Coordinator may nevertheless submit the other 'Parties' project deliverables and all other documents required by the GA to the FA in time.

4.2.- Work-package Teams

The Work-package teams are composed by all the beneficiaries working in a WP. They are led by the WP leader and co-leader, who will manage and be responsible for the overall performance of the WP and the timely delivery of Milestones and Deliverables. The WP leaders will be responsible for the management of the activities and coordination of the partners involved in their WP and to make the WP Progress Reports.

Every task inside of the WP has a Task Leader (TL) who will manage and be responsible for its results and compliance with the Project Planning. If detecting any incidence or risk in the development of the tasks, the Task leaders should report it to the WP leaders who will bring their opinion to the EB to safeguard the smooth progress of the adopted consensus-based decision-making process.

The deliverables should be sent in advance to the EB by the WP Leaders for their review. It is advisable to send the deliverables at least 15 days in advance of the due date in order to have time to solve any incidence.

4.3.- Executive Board

The Executive Board is considered the project's formal supervisory body for the execution of the project. It is composed by the Coordinator and the WP leaders and will monitor the Project progress and consensus-based decision-making. In case of WP Leader was the Coordinator, the WP co-Leader was designated as EB member. The appointment of the EB members was made during the Kick-off meeting (January 28th, 2021).

EXECUTIVE BOARD

Beneficiary	Leaded WP	Name
UTARTU	Coordinator	Tiit Kutser
dotSPACE	WP 1	Linda Van Duivenbode
VITO	WP 2	Ils Reusen
VUB	WP 3	Ann Van Griensven
EMU	WP 4	Alo Laas
IHE	WP 5	Ioana Popescu
USTIR	WP 6	Andrew Tyler
IsardSAT	WP 7	Maria José Escorihuela
3edata	WP 8	Carmen Cillero

Table 6.- Executive Board Appointees.

The Coordinator shall chair all meetings of the EB, unless decided otherwise by a majority of two-thirds.

The EB shall:

- prepare the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the GAs.
- seek a consensus among the Parties.
- be responsible for the proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the GAs.
- monitor the effective and efficient implementation of the Project.
- collect information at least every 6 months on the progress of the Project, examine that information to assess the compliance of the Project with the consortium plan and, if necessary, propose modifications of the consortium plan to the General Assembly.
- support the Coordinator in preparing meetings with the FA and in preparing related data and deliverables

- prepare the content and timing of press releases and joint publications by the consortium or proposed by the FA in respect of the procedures of the GA Article 29.

In the case of abolished tasks as a result of a decision of the GAs, the EB shall advise the GAs on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets of the Parties concerned. Such rearrangement shall take into consideration the legitimate commitments taken prior to the decisions, which cannot be cancelled.

If detecting or being informed by the Coordinator about any incidence or risk in the project implementation, the EB will decide the corrective management decisions to be taken to avoid delays and assure the correct flow of dependencies between tasks. The EB will also be supported by the AB. Any suggestion for improvement and other advice from the AB will be discussed in the EB and when possible integrated into the project.

4.4.- Advisory Board

The external expert Advisory Board (AB) will consist of a group of key experts and end-users working at leading international organizations in the field of earth observation and water resources management. The AB will meet with the EB to give opinion and advise about the progress of the project and shall assist and facilitate the decisions made by the GAs.

The AB will provide state-of-the-art knowledge and experience from scientific, policy and practical points of view, hereby helping to direct the activities in relation to stakeholder and end-user requirements.

The AB was appointed during the GA preparation and the Kick-off meeting (January 28th, 2021).

Names and affiliations of the external expert AB members:

- * Arnold Dekker. representative of GEOAquaWatch
- * Bastiaan Willem Ibelings. Chair of GLEON
- * ESA representative.
- * EEA representative.

4.5.- General Assembly

The **General Assembly** is considered the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium. In the GAs all the members of the consortium are represented. The appointment of the GAs members of the Water-ForCE was made during the Kick-off meeting (January 28th, 2021).

GENERAL ASSEMBLY

	Name
UTARTU	Tiit Kutser
DotSPACE	Linda Van Duivenbode
isardSAT	Maria José Escorihuela
ANTEA	Klaas Nijs
PML	Stefan Simis
FVB-IGB	Igor Ogashawara
GEOECOMAR	Adriana Maria Constantinescu
ICCS	Valantis Tsiakos
U STIRLING	Evangelos Spyrakos
IHE DELFT	Andreja Jonoski
EMU	Alo Laas
NIRDBS	Andrei Paun
VUB	Ann Van Griensven
3edata	Carmen Cillero
CNR	Claudia Giardino
VITO	Ils Reusen
BOKU	Thomas Hein
CREAF	Lluís Pesquer
SINERGISE	Grega Milzinski
WI	Steeff Peters

Table 7.- General Assembly Appointees.

4.6.- Communication and Dissemination Team

The Communication and Dissemination Team are the leaders of WP7 (isardSAT). They coordinate the overall stakeholder engagement, outreach activities and dissemination of the results.

WP7 will enable tools and means for raising awareness, extend the impact of the Action, engage stakeholders and target groups, share solutions and know-how, influence policy and practice, and develop new partnerships. This will be achieved through the following four tasks:

- development of a dissemination and communication plan;
- development of a webpage and an effective communication toolkit;
- organization of project workshops;
- dissemination of project results in relevant networks and influencing places and to the scientific community.

4.7.- Meetings and Procedures

Any Party which is a member of a Consortium Body (EB, GAs):

- should be present or represented at any meeting;
- may appoint a substitute or a proxy to attend and vote at any meeting;
- shall participate in a cooperative manner in the meetings.

The planned frequency for the meetings is different for every Consortium Body:

The EB will have periodic (quarterly) meetings and at any time upon written request of any member of the EB. To reduce travel expenses, the EB will meet physically 3 times; 2 of them during the proposed big networking events (M6 & M33) and one in the middle of the project coinciding with a suitable WP meeting. If the first event should be held remotely due to travel restrictions (COVID19), then a new suitable date will be decided for this physical meeting. The rest of the meetings will be organized as teleconference.

The **GAs** will have ordinary meetings at least once a year and when major decisions for the progress of the project should be taken and in which all of the members of the consortium should be involved simultaneously. The GAs will meet at any time upon written request of the EB or 1/3 of the members of the GAs, in order to maximize that the consensus-based decision-making is fully applied.

The **AB** will have periodic meetings with the EB (twice a year). They will meet physically twice with the whole consortium during the project in the two big networking events to be held at the start (M6) and at the end (M33) of the project. If the first event should be held remotely due to travel restrictions (COVID19), then a new suitable date will be decided for this physical meeting.

The notice for a meeting of a Consortium Body should be given in writing to each member of that Consortium Body as soon as possible and no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Notice of a meeting		
	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary Meeting
General Assembly	45 calendar days	15 calendar days
Executive Board	14 calendar days	7 calendar days

Table 8.- Meeting notice period.

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall prepare and send each member of that Consortium Body a written (original) **agenda, with the provided Water-ForCE template**, no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below:

Sending the Agenda		
	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary Meeting
General Assembly	21 calendar days	10 calendar days
Executive Board	7 calendar days	7 calendar days

Table 9.- Period for sending the agenda.

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the members of a Consortium Body must be identified as such on the agenda.

Any member of a Consortium Body may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other members of that Consortium Body up to the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Adding Agenda Items		
	Ordinary Meeting	Extraordinary Meeting
General Assembly	7 calendar days	3 calendar days
Executive Board	2 calendar days	2 calendar days

Table 10.- Period for adding agenda items.

During a meeting, the members of a Consortium Body present or represented can unanimously agree to add a new item to the original agenda.

Each Consortium Body shall not deliberate and decide validly unless two-thirds (2/3) of its members are present or represented (quorum). If the quorum is not reached, the chairperson of the Consortium Body shall convene another ordinary meeting within 15 calendar days. If in this meeting the quorum is not reached once more, the chairperson shall convene an extraordinary meeting which shall be entitled to decide even if less than the quorum of members are present or represented.

Decisions will only be binding once the relevant part of the Minutes has been accepted. Any decision may also be taken without a meeting if the Coordinator circulates to all members of the Consortium Body a written document, which is then agreed by the defined majority of all members of the Consortium Body. Such document shall include the deadline for responses.

Conflict Resolution. If necessary, the CT will organize a conflict resolution meeting within 30 days following the reception of a written request from any of the project partners. Attempts at arbitration will be performed in increasing order of authority:

- within the team of each WP under the management of the WP Leader;

- under management of the Coordinator; and
- within the EB under management of the Coordinator.

Any risks and discrepancy within WP's shall be first resolved on WP level by the means of dialogue and mutual consensus. In case a consensus cannot be reached, decisions from higher levels will be requested.

The decisions inside of the consortium will be consensus-based. When the consensus cannot be achieved, the majority vote will be applied (two-thirds (2/3) of the votes cast).

The chairperson of a Consortium Body shall produce written **minutes of each meeting** which shall be the formal record of all decisions taken. He/she shall send the draft minutes to all Members within 10 calendar days of the meeting.

The minutes shall be considered as accepted if, within 15 calendar days from sending, no member has sent an objection in writing to the chairperson with respect to the accuracy of the draft of the minutes.

The chairperson shall send the accepted minutes to all the members of the Consortium Body and to the Coordinator, who shall safeguard them. If requested the Coordinator shall provide authenticated duplicates to Parties.

The minutes of EB meetings, once accepted, shall be sent by the Coordinator to the GAs members for information.

The final version of the meeting minutes of every meeting (WP, Task, Consortium Bodies) should be uploaded by the WPL or TL to the dedicated folder of the WP in the Shared Google Drive Units, together with the documents used during the meeting (agenda, presentations,...):

Shared unit: WF_WPX/WPX_Meetings

Consortium Bodies meeting minutes will be uploaded to the WP8 folder.

5.- Project Communication Strategy

5.1.- Internal communication

3edata has created a shared document space in the cloud using Google Drive Shared Units feature. It will be used for all official project documentation, calling notices, agenda, meeting minutes, working documents and deliverables.

5.1.1 Consortium contact List

A contact list has been created and distributed to all partners through the shared Google Drive Space. This list is available as an excel worksheet.

Shared Unit: WF_0_DOCUMENTS/0_Consortium_Docs/Contacts

The contact list is maintained by the Project Manager and includes email addresses of all the people involved in the project. It also Includes Information about the role of every participant regarding their WP involvement; the professional profile inside of the project (Technical/Administrative-Financial/Dissemination and Communication); membership of Consortium Bodies and access details to the Common Google Drive Shared Space.

The contact list breaks down the WP in which each contact has more than 1 persons/month of workload. This is intended to prevent the proliferation of emails and broadcasting to the whole consortium. Where possible consortium members should only email the contacts to whom the email is relevant and emails to all should be minimized.

5.1.2 External contacts List

The external contact lists, mostly dedicated to workshop attendees, will be managed through a CRM (Customer Relation Management) tool (Hubspot) (see 5.2.1).

5.1.3 Conferencing platforms

3edata has at the disposal of the project 3 different professional conferencing platforms:

- Zoom
- Google Meet
- Microsoft Teams

The most suitable platform will be used in every meeting depending on the preferences/needs of the majority of the attendees.

5.1.4 Document sharing platform

The chosen document sharing platform is Google Drive. Nine different Shared Units have been enabled, one for every WP and one for the General Documents of the consortium.

Figure 3.- Scheme of the shared space in Google Drive

In every Shared Unit there are 2 Managers: one of them is the WPL and the other is 3edata who created the folder. The rest of the WP Team will have "Content Manager" privileges. To see the different access levels and the actions they can perform see Figure 4.

Every member of the consortium has the right of having access to any of these folders. The initial action was to give access to the Documents Unit and the WP

Unit in which the partner has more than 1 p/m of workload, but access to any folder will be given upon request to the Project Manager.

Task	Access level				
	Manager	Content manager*	Contributor**	Commenter	Viewer
View shared drives, files, and folders	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Comment on files in shared drives	✓	✓	✓	✓	✗
Make, approve, and reject edits in files	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
Create and upload files and create folders in shared drives	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
Add people and groups to specific <i>files</i> in shared drives	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗
Add people and groups to specific <i>folders</i> in shared drives	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Move files and folders within a shared drive	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Move files and folders from one shared drive to another shared drive	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Move shared drive files and folders into the trash	✓	✓	✗	✗	✗
Permanently delete files and folders in the trash	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
Restore files and folders from trash (up to 30 days)	✓	✓	✓	✗	✗

Figure 4.- Different access levels and actions inside a shared Google Drive Unit. (Source: <https://support.google.com/>)

5.1.5 Shared Calendar

A common calendar (**Water-ForCE Calendar**) has been enabled (Private Google Calendar) with access to all partners. This will serve as a tool for facilitating the communication, information sharing and collaboration between Consortium Members and between WPs.

All the Important dates will be added to this common calendar by the Project Manager: reporting periods, meetings, workshops, conferences and major events considered important for the project.

WPL and TL shall send to the PM the planned meeting/workshop's dates with a tentative agenda to be attached to the event. This will ensure that any member of the consortium interested in attending to any WP meeting will be duly informed. The calendar will also serve as an information source regarding major events and conferences which would be interesting for the project development. Any Consortium Member who considers that an event should be highlighted, shall send this Information to the PM who will circulate It among the rest of Consortium members and add it in into the calendar, Including Important dates and deadlines, when possible.

5.2.- External Communication and Dissemination

5.2.1 CRM Tool

A CRM Tool (Hubspot) will be used to manage and access external contacts (stakeholders and relevant participants to workshops and dissemination events) in a General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliant way.

The CRM Tool will work behind the **@waterforce.eu** domain and every WP will have a distinctive account to keep track on the original source of every contact. This will maintain the needed trust between the contact and the contact provider.

The CRM Tool will be used to capture stakeholder information as part of T1.1, allowing to sort the Workshop's participants into categories and send emails to different lists in a GDPR compliant way, minimizing the risk of SPAM.

5.2.2 Stakeholders workshops and communication

Inside of WP7 (Communication and Dissemination), the Task 7.3 will work on organization of users and stakeholder workshops.

The mechanism for communicating with Water-ForCE stakeholders will be meetings of the community. Six main workshops are scheduled, one per each thematic/technical working group in WP2-WP4 and two large open international workshops. The first large workshop will be an open international workshop organised within WP1 that will synthesize the initial findings of the WP1 and provide tasks to the technical WP's (WP2-WP5). This first meeting was initially scheduled by M6. If this first event should be held remotely due to travel restrictions (COVID19), then a new suitable date could be decided by the consortium for a presential meeting.

Each of the technical WPs will gather a working group and will organize one thematic workshop (See Fig. 2 and Annex 1 for the timing of every workshop).

A final open international workshop, where the first draft of the Roadmap will be discussed and analyzed, will be organized together with WP6 (M33).

A Communication toolkit, with corporate image and leitmotiv, will be produced inside of WP7-Task 7.2. (M3). The communication toolkit will provide template materials and outcomes from different communities to engage further exchanges with stakeholders. The template materials will include key messages and visuals as well as suggested materials for use by local, national and EU levels.

All the materials will be at the disposal of the partners in the Shared Unit of WP7.

5.2.3 Website

The website for the project will be enabled by month 3 (March, 2021) behind the domain:

www.waterforce.eu

This website will provide the Water-ForCE participants with easy exchange of documentation of results and information, and the EC and other users with a central place to follow the progress of the project and provide timely user feedbacks.

5.2.4 Social Media

The main Social Media to be used in the Water-ForCE will be twitter. A twitter account was enabled during the Kick-off meeting (January 26-28th, 2021):

[@H2020WaterForCE](https://twitter.com/H2020WaterForCE)

The twitter account is ruled by the WP7 leader (IsardSAT).

5.2.5 Dissemination

The Dissemination and Communication Plan will be developed in WP7 (M6) in close collaboration with WP1. It will start at the beginning of the project to ensure that strong and effective lines of communication are established with key

stakeholders. The purpose is to ensure reaching a large and rich community as possible and capture their respective wide range of requirements.

The scientific community will be informed mainly through attendance to workshops organised by Water-ForCE and other relevant international organisations as well as through conferences where the objectives of the project will be explained and the feedback from the community will be sought.

The main output of the Water-ForCE will be the Roadmap for Copernicus Inland Water Services. The WP7 will take care that this document will be distributed to policy makers at the EU and national levels, relevant Copernicus Services, monitoring agencies (EEA and national ones), space agencies (ESA and national ones).

The dissemination of the project outcomes and any publications should respect the agreed dissemination of each consortium partner's foreground, Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) and data as it is stated in the CA.

During the Project and for a period of 1 year after the end of the Project, the dissemination of own results by one or several Parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 29.1 of the GA subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the GA in writing to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

Disseminations shall always duly acknowledge Water-ForCE, refer to the grant number, use the logo, and either co-author or duly acknowledge partners that were involved in generating the results, depending on what is suitable.

All communication activities related to the action must:

- display the EU emblem and

- include the following text: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004186”*

6.- Document Management

During the course of the Water-ForCE project many documents will be consulted and produced; therefore, an organized document management structure is important in order to enable users to locate and identify relevant files.

6.1.- Document Storage

The documents will be stored in the Google Drive Shared Units, following the structure below:

Document Storage Structure		
Top Level Folder	Sub folder	Content
WF_0_DOCUMENTS	0_Consortium Docs	Final versions of GA, CA and contact list
	1_Templates	Templates for deliverables, meeting agenda and minutes, presentations and time sheets
	2_Progress Monitoring	Progress monitoring reports of every WP.
	3_Partners	Presentations and logos.
	4_General Presentations	General presentations of Water-ForCE
WF_1_Common Work Space		Shared unit to be used freely by the partners to share information or develop common working documents of the interest of the whole consortium.
WF_WPX	Meetings	Minutes, presentations and agenda
	Repository	External documents storage area
	Work Space	Draft documents and reports
	Final Deliverables	

Table 11.- Document Storage Structure. WF-WPX indicates the same structure for every WP from 1 to 8.

6.2.- Templates

Templates will be provided both by the Communication and Dissemination Team and Coordination Team for the following document types:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Meeting Agenda (MS Word format)
- Meeting Minutes (MS Word format)
- Presentations (MS Power Point format)
- Timesheets (MS Excel format)

All official project documents should use these templates. These templates may be updated and/or redesigned. Therefore, consortium partners should download the most up to date version from the 0_DOCUMENTS/1_Templates sub folder.

6.3.- File Formats

To facilitate the exchange of documents between partners, the following file formats are recommended inside of the consortium:

- Word processor documents: MS Word format
- Spreadsheet documents: MS Excel format
- Presentations: MS Power Point format
- Promotional materials (flyers, newsletters) or other non-editable project documents: PDF format
- For compressed files: .zip; .rar format
- Bitmap image files: JPEG or PNG formats

6.4.- Document coding

A common structure to name the files and documents will facilitate their management and identification. The proposed structure is as follows:

WPX-Document type and number-DATE(AAAAMMDD)-Version number-status

where:

- WPX: WP number
- Document type: agenda, minutes, deliverable or presentation
- Document number: If any
- Status: Draft, Final

Example of a the deliverable D8.1:

WP8_D8.1_20210131_V.1_Draft

7.- Internal Project Monitoring

It is the responsibility of the Coordinator to assure the quality and smooth developing of the project. He will be assisted in this task by the EB (which is the project's formal supervisory body for the execution of the project) and by the Project Manager.

7.1.- Progress reports

Each WP leader will report project progress to the Coordination Team on Month 4 and 9 of every year. This will cover technical progress, results, deliverables and compliance with the WP schedule, as well as the monitoring and updating of the identified risks.

Templates for Progress Reports will be available in the dedicated folder inside of WF_0_Documents Shared Unit.

Shared Unit: WF_0_DOCUMENTS/1-TEMPLATES

This progress reports should be uploaded to their dedicated WP folder inside of:

Shared Unit: WF_0_DOCUMENTS/2-PROGRESS MONITORING

to be revised and validated by the Coordination Team and EB.

All Progress reports will be available for the consortium in this shared units. The Coordinator shall inform about the overall progress of the WPs and hence of the Action to the consortium during GAs meetings.

7.2.- Periodic Management Reports

The Coordination Team will deliver 3 periodic management reports during the project on an annual basis (M12, M24 & M36). The following content is expected:

- SUMMARY: project objectives and achievements for the reporting period
- Description of the general objectives of the project
- Description of the results and progress of every WP
- Status of Deliverables and Milestones
- Project Management progress
- Used resources

These Project Management Reports will be based upon the WP progress reports but some extra input might be needed from WP Leaders. All partners shall provide justifications if deviations from their budget plan have occur.

7.3.- Review and submission of Deliverables

The EB is the project's formal supervisory body. All deliverables shall be made available in advance to the Project Manager (at least 15 days before due date are advised) for her to distribute them to the EB. Among the EB members, 2 people will be appointed to be the main reviewers of each deliverable attending to their main field of expertise and knowledge, related to the deliverable content.

The deliverables shall be reviewed within a period of 5 working days and made available to the main author/editor. The main author/editor and contributors to the deliverable shall provide amendments according to the received comments. A history of changes of the document should be kept.

The final deliverables shall be uploaded to the dedicated folder inside of every WP shared unit.

All the beneficiaries can upload deliverables but only the Coordinator is the responsible for submitting them to the EC. The submission to the EC will be done through the Participant Portal.

8.- Financial Management

8.1.- Financial Reporting

8.1.1 Internal Financial Reporting

The project's internal financial reporting aims at keeping track of the project's costs per partner, per cost category and per WP to ensure sound financial management throughout the course of the action.

An internal financial report shall be sent by every partner to the Coordination Team every 6 months if the dates are not coincident with the formal financial reporting to EC (See Table 12).

A template will be provided for each beneficiary to enter their costs during the period. This template can be used as a basis for the formal reporting.

This internal financial information will be summarized by the Coordination Team to compare the actual expenditure against the budget included in the workplan. This will facilitate the consortium to organize their finances according to the project progress and detect any risk or need on time.

8.1.2 Financial Reporting to EC

Water-ForCE Action has 2 formal periodic reporting periods (M12 and M36). The Financial Report should be submitted by the Coordinator within 60 days of the end of each reporting period (including the final one), including requests for payment.

The periodic financial report consists of structured forms from the grant management system, including:

- individual financial statements (Annex 4 to the GA) for each beneficiary (and third parties)
- explanation of the use of resources and the information on subcontracting and in-kind contributions provided by third parties, from each beneficiary for the reporting period concerned.
- periodic summary financial statement including the request for payment.

All beneficiaries must fill in their own financial statements in the Participant Portal within 30 days after the end of the periodic reporting period for the coordination team to revise for compliance. The Individual Financial Statements of each beneficiary shall be signed electronically by the corresponding Project Financial Signatories (PFSIGN) appointed by each organization.

Financial Reporting			
	Internal reporting	Formal reporting to EC	Payments
M6	X		
M12		X	Interim
M18	X		
M24	X		
M30	X		
M36		X	P. of the Balance

Table 12.- Financial reporting calendar

8.2.- Payments

8.2.1 Payments from the EC

There are 3 types of payments (Art 21 GA): Pre-financing, Interim payment and Payment of the balance (Final).

The Water-ForCE Action had a **pre-financing payment** of the 80% of the maximum grant amount, from which the amount corresponding to 5% of the maximum grant amount was transferred to the Guarantee Fund.

The **interim payment** will reimburse the eligible costs incurred for the implementation of the action during the corresponding reporting period (M1 to M12). After the reporting period (**M12**), if the financial report is approved, the EC makes an interim payment within 90 days of receiving the interim report. The total of the pre-financing and the interim payment may not exceed 90% of the maximum grant amount, and only the payment of the balance can reimburse the remaining amount of eligible costs.

The **payment of the balance** will be made at the end of the project (**M36**). It reimburses the remaining amount of eligible costs incurred by the Beneficiaries for the implementation of the action. It is a balance so, if the total amount of earlier payments is lower than the final grant amount, the EC will pay the balance within 90 days of receiving the final report. Final payment is done upon the approval of the final report. The amount retained in the Guarantee Fund is also released at the payment of the balance.

8.2.2 Distribution of funds to the consortium members

The EC financial contribution is received by the Coordinator on behalf of the consortium. The Coordinator shall distribute the EC financial contribution to each partner without unjustified delay according to the rules set out in the CA and GA.

9.- Reporting and Reviews - EC

The **review planning** for the Water-ForCE Action comprises:

- 1st periodic review (M12; Jan-Feb 2022)
- interim technical review (M24)
- periodic final review (M36; Jan-Feb 2024)

Under Art 19 and 20 of GA, the coordinator must submit to the EC **technical and financial reports**, including requests for payment - specifically:

- **deliverables** identified in Annex 1
- **periodic report** (both technical and financial) within 60 days of the end of each reporting period (including the final one), including requests for payment
- **final report** at the end of the project. It consisting in a summary for publication and it is generated automatically by the IT tools.

9.1.- Continuous reporting

The continuous reporting module in the Funding and Tenders Portal is activated at the time the project starts and it is continuously open for the beneficiaries to submit information about the progress of the project. This includes:

- deliverables
- progress in achieving milestones
- updates in the publishable summary
- response to critical risks, publications, communications activities, IPRs
- answers to the questionnaire about the economic and social impact of the project.

All this information is automatically compiled to create part A of every technical periodic report, at the moment the coordinator and beneficiaries finish the preparation of the given periodic report.

All beneficiaries can upload the deliverables but only the Coordinator can submit them. EU officers are notified about the uploading of the deliverables. If any deliverable is rejected, there will be a notification from the EC side.

9.2.- Periodic Reporting

The periodic report module in the Funding and Tenders Portal is activated at the end of the reporting period to allow the beneficiaries to complete on-line their own Financial Statement and upload the Part B of the Technical report as a pdf.

The Water-ForCE CSA will have two periodic reports: one that will comprise the period between the start of the project (01/01/2021) and M12 (31/12/2021); and one final periodic report from M13 (01/01/2022) to M36 (31/12/2023). They shall be delivered and submitted by the Coordinator within 60 days after the end of the reporting period.

The periodic reports consist of:

Technical report (in 2 parts)

- Part A structured tables from the grant management system:
 - cover page
 - publishable summary
 - web-based tables covering issues related to the project implementation (e.g. work packages, deliverables, milestones, etc.)
 - answers to the questionnaire about the economic and social impact, especially as measured against the Horizon 2020 key performance indicators and monitoring requirements.

- Part B the free text, core part of the report. It should be uploaded to the grant management tool as a single PDF document with:
 - explanations of the work carried out by all beneficiaries and linked third parties during the reporting period
 - an overview of the progress towards the project objectives, justifying the differences between work expected under Annex I and work actually performed, if any.
 - updated risk management and mitigation solutions (compilation of the information provided in the continuous reporting 9.1), impact KPIs (targeted and achieved values), Open Science practices and IP management issues.

Financial report (see section 8.1.2)

The official Periodic Report Template from the EC is available for the consortium partners inside of the Documents Shared Unit:

Shared Unit: WF_0_DOCUMENTS/1_TEMPLATES

The coordinator will launch the process of gathering the needed input from the beneficiaries to deliver the Periodic Report on M12 and M36. Technical information will be needed from the WP Leaders who will provide a WP progress report for the period not later than one month after the end of the period (M13 and M37).

9.3.- Final Report

For the final reporting period, in addition to the submission of the periodic report of the last reporting period, a final report is generated automatically by the IT tool.

The final report consists of 2 parts - both of which must be completed in the grant management system (no need to upload any documents):

Final technical report:

Publishable summary of the entire project (giving an overview of the results, their exploitation and dissemination, and the conclusions about the project and its socio-economic impact; updated risk management and mitigation solutions, impact KPIs (targeted and achieved values), Open Science practices and IP management issues)

Final financial report:

Final summary financial statement consolidating the individual financial statements for all the reporting periods. It is automatically created by the system and corresponds to the request for payment of the balance.

9.4.- Report on the distribution of payments

After having received the final payment from the EC, the Coordinator shall submit a report on the distribution of the EU financial contribution between beneficiaries within 30 days after reception of the final payment.

Annex 1

Detailed Gantt Chart

